

TADBIRKORLIKNING MAZMUN-MOHIYATI VA UNI KATEGORIYALASH

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Tadbirkorlik va biznes har bir mamlakatning rivojlanishi uchun muhim rol o'ynaydi. Usiz hech qaysi mamlakat ayniqsa kapitalistik iqtisodiy tizimni o'zi uchun asosiy yo'nalish sifatida tanlagan mamlakatlarda rivojlana olmaydi. Chunki, tadbirkorlik faoliyati har qanday mamlakatda iqtisodiy rivojlanish, hamda aholi farovonligini ta'minlashda juda dolzarb ahamiyat ega soha hisoblanadi. Xitoy kabi tez suratlarda o'sayotgan mamlakatlarda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining YaIM dagi ulushi 60% tashkil etadi¹. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki har qanday mamlakatning iqtisodiy o'sishini ta'minlash undagi tadbirkorlik faoliyati rivojlanishiga bog'liq. 1991-yillarda endigina mustaqil bo'lgan O'zbekiston uchun tadbirkorlik faoliyati juda achinarli ahvolda edi, lekin to'g'ri amalga oshirilgan sa'y-harakatlar tufayli 2019-yilga kelib tadbirkorlik faoliyati mamlakat YaIM ning 50% ni tashkil etmoqda².

ASOSIY MATN

Barchamiz "Biznes" so'zi yaqindagina o'zbek tilida iste'molga kirganligini bilamiz. Ba'zida ushbu so'z "Tadbirkorlik" so'zi bilan teng ma'noda qo'llanilganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Chunki, ma'lum materiallarni o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilishda, tarjima qiluvchi shaxs imkoni boricha ajnabiy bo'lmagan so'zlardan hammaga tushunarli bo'lishi uchun foydalanishga harakat qiladi. Ammo, ushbu holatda xatoga yo'l qo'ygan bo'ladi. "Biznes" qadimgi inglizcha so'z *besignes*dan olingan bo'lib uning iste'moli milodiy 950-yillarga to'g'ri keladi. Ushbu so'zning semantikasiga qaraydigan bo'lsak inglizcha "Busy" so'zi "Biror ish bilan shug'ullanish" va "-ness" ya'ni "-lik" ma'nosini beruvchi ot so'z turkumini yasovchi qo'shimchasi birikmasidan hosil bo'lgan bo'lib umumiy holdagi "Biznes" so'zi "*Biror ish bilan band bo'lishlik*"³ degan ma'no hosil qiladi. Biznes bilan shug'ullanuvchi shaxs *businessmen* deyiladi. *Biznes* so'zining kelib chiqishi ingliz tilida *tadbirkorlik* so'ziga teng ma'noda "Entrepreneurship" so'zi ishlatilib *biznes* so'zi bilan doimo teng ma'noda ishlatilmaydi. Oksford o'quvchilari lug'atida "*biznes*" so'zi *pul topish maqsadida tovarlar va xizmatlarni*

¹ <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/a3891ad8-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/a3891ad8-en#:~:text=In%20China%2C%20there%20were%20over,reached%2022%20000%20per%20day.>

² <https://stat.tjz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/22643-kichik-tadbirkorlik-biznes-ning-yaimdagi-uhushi-3>

³ <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/business>

ishlab chiqarish, sotib olish, sotish hamda ta'minlash bilan shug'ullanadigan faoliyat, "Tadbirkorlik" so'zi esa ayniqsa moliyaviy tavakkalchilikni taqqozo etadigan biznesni boshlash hamda uni yurgazish orqali pul topish faoliyati sifatida tasvirlangan⁴.

Iqtisodiyotda biznes tovarlar va xizmatlarni sotib olish, hamda sotish masalasidagi barcha uchun umumiy bo'lgan faoliyatni o'zida mujassamlashtiradigan bo'lsa, tadbirkorlik yangi korxonalarni vujudga keltirish, rivoji uchun sa'y-harakatlarni amalga oshirish hamda uni boshqarishga yo'naltirilgan faoliyat hisoblanadi⁵.

Chizma 1. Tadbirkorlikning asosiy talablari.

⁴ <https://OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com>

⁵ [Ngo, H.T.T.](#) and [Igwe, P.A.](#) (2019), "Internationalization of Firms and Entrepreneur's Motivations: A Review and Research Agenda", [Dana, L.-P.](#) and [Ratten, V.](#) (Ed.) *Societal Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 29-46.

“Tadbirkorlik” innovatsion biznes g`oyalarni amaliyotga joriy etish va yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo`lgan muammolarga yechimtopish jarayoni bo`lib har qanday tadbirkorlikni boshqarishda uning turiga e`tibor qaratish lozim va tadbirkorlik faoliyatini quyidagi turlarga bo`lish o`rinlidir⁶:

1. Kichik tadbirkorlik faoliyati;
2. Kengaytirilgan start-ap loyihalarga asoslangan tadbirkorlik;
3. Katta kompaniya tadbirkorligi;
4. Ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik;
5. Tadqiqot tadbirkorligi;
6. Xarid tadbirkorligi

Kichik biznes tadbirkorligi – kichik biznes korxonasini tashkil etish, boshqarish va rivojlantirish jarayoni bo`liob bunday turdagi tadbirkorlik asosan bozorning cheklangan segmentiga mahalliy korxonalar sifatida faoliyat yuritishni o`z ichiga olib asosan kamyob tovar va xizmatlar bilan ham mahalliy bozorni ta`minlashi mumkin⁷.

Kengaytirilgan startap loyahasiga asoslangan tadbirkorlik-bu innovatsion va katta daromad keltiruvchi g`oyadan boshlanadigan va tezda katta daromadli kompaniyaga aylana oladigan unumli biznes modelini qabul qiladigan tadbirkorlik turi bo`lib uning asosiy vazifasi katta bozorga chiqish va kompaniya taklif qiladigan tovar va xizmatlar uchun joy yaratishdir⁸. Kengaytirilgan startap

⁶ Rosemaro, Elena. (2022). Understanding the Concept of Entrepreneurship Management and Its Contribution in Organization. International Journal of New Practices in Management and Engineering. 11. 24-30. 10.17762/ijnpme.v11i01.159.

⁷ Eunice, Arenu & Epetimehin, Festus. (2020). Motivation of Women Entrepreneurs in Nigeria. Sumerianz Journal of Social Science. 162-170. 10.47752/sjss.312.162.170.

⁸<https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/management/scalability/#:~:text=A%20scalable%20startup%20is%20one,niche%20for%20the%20company's%20products>

loyihasiga asoslangan tadbirkorlikka Facebook, Instagram, Airbnb, Spotify, Uber⁹ kabilarni misol keltirishimiz mumkin. Osiyo Taraqqiyot bankining 2020-yildagi keltirgan ma'lumotiga ko'ra O'zbekistonda taxminan 1200 startap loyihalar yo'lga qo'yilgan¹⁰ bo'lib ularning eng ko'p daramod keltirayotganlaridan bittasi butun O'zbekiston bo'ylab mijozlarga elektron xarid qilish, o'z biznesini rivojlantirish, to'lovlarni qayta ishlash va oziq-ovqat yetkazib berishni tashkil qilish imkonini beradigan "Uzum" startapi hisoblanadi¹¹.

Katta kompaniya tadbirkorligi- biznes doirasida yangi korxonalarini rivojlantirish, innovatsiyalardan foydalanish, kompaniya miqyosidagi o'sishni amalga oshirish yo'lidagi operatsiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi¹². Katta kompaniya tadbirkorligining boshqa tadbirkorliklardan muhim ustunliklaridan biri shuki, unda yangi texnologiya va g'oyalardan foydalanish imkonini beruvchi tadqiqot va rivojlanishga sarmoya kiritish uchun moliyaviy resurslar mavjud¹³. Ikkinchidan, katta kompaniyalarda resurslar tajriba va yangi bozorlarni baholash imkonini berishi mumkin bo'lgan mavjud tarmoqlar sherikchilik aloqalari yo'lga qo'yilgan bo'ladi. Jahon miqyosida Google, Microsoft, Apple va Samsung kabi kompaniyalarni katta kompaniyalar sirasiga kirish mumkin¹⁴.

Ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik- ijtimoiy muammolarga yechim topish va ijtimoiy talablarga javob beradigan tadbirkorlik prinsiplari va strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning asosiy maqsadi foydani maksimallashtirishdan ko'ra ijtimoiy qiymatga yo'naltirilgan korxonani loyihalashtirish, ishga tushirish hamda uni boshqarishdan iborat. Ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik faoliyati asosan qashshoqlikni kamaytirish, sog'liqni saqlash, ta'lim va atrof-muhitni himoyalashdagi muammolarni hal etishga yo'naltirilgan notijorat tashkilotlar shaklida bo'lishi mumkin¹⁵. Dunyo bo'ylab ko'plab ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik faoliyati bilan shug'ullanadigan tashkilotlar bor bo'lib ularga Tom's Shoes, State Bags, Warby Parker, Trinity Oaks, Ashoka va Mitscoots¹⁶ kabilarni misol keltirish mumkin.

⁹ <https://joeducation.eu/digital-startups-examples-what-they-are/>

¹⁰ <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/905251/uzbekistan-ecosystem-technology-startups.pdf>

¹¹ <https://techround.co.uk/tech/10-startups-in-uzbekistan-to-watch/>

¹² Nabila, Azwa, Ambad., Kalsom, Abd. (2013). Corporate entrepreneurship as a determinant of large firm performance.

¹³ Tseng, Jauling. (2020). How do finance companies' advantages affect competitive strategies in short- and intermediate-term loan markets? A theoretical analysis. International Journal of Finance & Economics. 26. 10.1002/ijfe.2014.

¹⁴ <https://www.pfh.de/en/blog/9-types-entrepreneurship#:~:text=Large%20company%20entrepreneurship&text=Large%20companies%20often%20create%20new,of%20the%20kind%20of%20entrepreneurship.>

¹⁵ Akbulaev, Nurkhodzha & Aliyev, Yusif & Ahmadov, Turan. (2019). Research models for financing social business: theory and practice. Heliyon. 5. e01599. 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01599.

¹⁶ <https://www.consciousconnectionmagazine.com/2016/02/social-enterprise-examples-and-principles/>

Tadqiqot tadbirkorligi- innovatsion g'oyalarni va kashfiyotlarni tijoriy tovar va xizmatlarga o'zgartirish orqali akademik tadqiqot va bozor o'rtasidagi bo'shliqni to'ldirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu orqali tadqiqotchilarning chuqur izlanishlari iqtisodiy qiymat yaratishda va jamiyat rivojiga turtki bo'ladi. Tadqiqot tadbirkorligi faoliyatiga jalb etilgan PhD talabalari va magistrantlar startap loyihalar va texnologiyalarni yo'lga qo'yishda amaliy dunyo haqidagi maxsus bilimlarini qo'llash orqali platformalarni ishlab chiqishlari mumkin. Tadqiqot orqali tadbirkorlikni amalga oshirish uchun faqatgina kuchli akademik salohiyat yetarli bo'lib qolmasdan balki haqiqiy tadbirkor kabi fikrlash, bozor dinamikasini tushunish muhim hisoblanadi¹⁷. *Xarid tadbirkorligi*- yangi biznesni boshlashga sarmoya kiritmasdan kichik biznes yoki kompaniyani sotib olish orqali undan foyda olishni qamrab olgan faoliyatdir¹⁸. Bunga 2022-yil 14-aprelda Elon Maskning "Twitter" ni sotib olganligini va uni yanada rivojlantirganligini misol keltirish mumkin¹⁹.

XULOSA

Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, tadbirkorlik tadbirkorlik faoliyati tegishli tarzda amalga oshiriladigan ma'lum bir mamlakatga ko'maklashish imkoniyatlarini ta'minlash uchun juda muhimdir. Aks holda, tadbirkorlik faoliyati samarasiz deb hisoblanishi mumkin. Avvalo, tadbirkorlikning o'ziga xos usulini tanlab olish kerak, keyin esa u chuqur bilim va tajribaga ega bo'lishi kerak, chunki ularning har biri bilan tadbirkorlik faoliyatini amalga oshirish mumkin emas.

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¹⁷ [Career Planning for PhDs ebook](#) n.d.

¹⁸ Rosemaro, Elena. (2022). Understanding the Concept of Entrepreneurship Management and Its Contribution in Organization. International Journal of New Practices in Management and Engineering. 11. 24-30. 10.17762/ijnpm.v11i01.159.

¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Acquisition_of_Twitter_by_Elon_Musk#:~:text=Business%20magnate%20Elon%20Musk%20initiated,mimic%20the%20Chinese%20app%20WeChat.

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